

Research Article

Nursing Student's Perception and their Future Intentions

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Abstract: Background: Nursing is defined as the protection, promotion, and optimisation of health and abilities, prevention of illness and injury, alleviation of suffering through the diagnosis and treatment of human response, advocacy in the care of individuals, families, communities, and populations.¹ Nursing is widely regarded as a noble profession in the society because of the core value it promotes in its practice-which is the care of life³. **Methods:** Simple random sampling technique was used and samples of 100 students who are from colleges at Bangalore were selected. The tool which contains 10 demographic variables and Self-Administered Questionnaire was administered. The Statistical analysis was done by using descriptive and inferential statistics. **Results:** Present study found that out of 100 subjects, (40%) had 'Good' perception (60%) had 'Average' perception. The hypothesis states that there is no relationship between outgoing B.Sc. nursing student's perception towards their profession with their demographic variables. So the hypothesis H₁ were accepted.

Keywords: Perception, Future Intentions, Nursing students.

Introduction

Nursing is defined as the protection, promotion, and optimization of health and abilities, prevention of illness and injury, alleviation of suffering through the diagnosis and treatment of human response, advocacy in the care of individuals, families, communities, and populations.¹ It is also defined as the use of clinical judgment in the provision of care to enable people to improve, maintain, or recover health, to cope with health problems, and to achieve the best possible quality of care, whatever their disease or disability, until death². Nursing is widely regarded as a noble profession in the society because of the core value it promotes in its practice-which is the care of life³. This study was undertaken to assess the nursing student's perception and their future intentions in selected colleges at Bangalore.

Objectives

- 1) To find out the perception of outgoing B.Sc. nursing students towards nursing profession and carrier plans.
- 2) To identify the difference of perception based on socio-demographic variables.

Methods

Research approach used was descriptive approach which is a non-experimental design the study to assess the nursing student's perception and their future intentions in selected colleges at Bangalore.

Reliability of the tool was tested and validity was ensured in consultation with guides and experts in the fields of nursing.

The study was carried out in the samples of 100 students who are from colleges at Bangalore were selected by using simple random sampling technique. Collected data was analysed by using descriptive and inferential statistics.

Results and Discussion

Table 1. Demographic Characteristics of Students (N=100)

S/N	Demographic characteristics	Frequency	Percentage (%)	
1	Gender	Female	96	96.0
		Male	4	4.0
2	Religion	Hindu	84	84.0
		Muslim	2	2.0
		Christian	14	14.0
3	Habilitation	Urban	66	66.0
		Rural	34	34.0
4	Birth order	First	56	56.0
		Second	26	26.0
		Third	8	8.0
		Fourth	4	4.0
		Above	6	6.0
5	Nationality	Indian	94	94.0
		Other than Indian	6	6.0
6	Family members/Relatives in nursing	Yes	38	38.0
		No	62	62.0

Table 2. Family profile of students

S/N	Demographic characteristics	Frequency	Percentage (%)	
1	Education of Father	Illiterate	6	6.0
		Primary Education	14	14.0
		Secondary Education	44	44.0
		Degree	36	36.0
2	Education of Mother	Illiterate	10	10.0
		Primary Education	16	16.0
		Secondary Education	42	42.0
		Degree	32	32.0
3	Occupation of Father	Cultivation	20	20.0
		Daily wage worker	22	22.0
		Govt. Employee	20	20.0
		Private Employee	38	38.0
4	Occupation of Mother	Cooley	6	6.0
		House Wife	70	70.0
		Govt. Employee	16	16.0
		Private Employee	8	8.0

Table 3. Motivation to select nursing profession

S/N	Statement	Frequency	Percentage (%)	
1	Motivation to select nursing	Self-motivated	82	82.0
		By Parents	18	18.0
2	Opportunity to settle early	Yes	94	94.0
		No	6	6.0
3	Get Government, Jobs	Yes	80	80.0
		No	20	20.0
4	Earn Blessings	Yes	78	78.0
		No	22	22.0

Table 4. Perceptions of Nursing as a Profession

S/N	Nursing Profession is:	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	SD
1	A respectful profession	2.00	5.00	4.5800	.60603
2	An occupation and not a profession	1.00	5.00	2.7800	1.57365
3	A Women's profession	1.00	5.00	2.6600	1.41578
4	Similar to that of the servants' job.	1.00	4.00	1.6200	.77564
5	A well appreciated profession in the society	1.00	5.00	4.2600	1.07891
6	A prestigious profession	1.00	5.00	4.4000	.92113
7	A dangerous profession	1.00	5.00	2.4400	1.33576
8	An extremely hard profession that does not receive enough appreciation	1.00	5.00	3.4800	1.32177
9	An essential profession in any society	1.00	5.00	4.4600	.78393
10	Nursing is a human profession	1.00	5.00	4.4600	.83388
11	An independent profession by which nurses make decisions for themselves	1.00	5.00	3.7400	1.11573
12	A significant in patient's recovery	1.00	5.00	4.3400	.93441
13	Helping in promotion of health and prevention of diseases	1.00	5.00	4.4400	.75639
14	Provide self-actualization	3.00	5.00	4.2800	.77954
15	Nurses are given a chance to use their own initiative in their work	2.00	5.00	3.9800	1.14574
16	Nurses obey doctors' orders without questioning them	2.00	5.00	3.6800	1.05294
17	Nurses waste a lot of time being busy doing nothing	1.00	5.00	1.8200	1.09526
18	I would like my child to become a nurse	1.00	5.00	3.3000	1.24316
19	Anyone could be a nurse easy	1.00	5.00	2.1400	1.23926
20	Opportunity for personal growth	3.00	5.00	4.6000	.53182
21	Caring profession in which ethical standards of care is maintained	1.00	5.00	4.3200	.90877
22	Actually equal to other professions	1.00	5.00	2.7600	1.23190

Table 5. Level of perception towards nursing perception among outgoing B.Sc. Nursing students

Level of perception	Frequency	Percentage
Good perception	40	40.0
Average perception	60	60.0
Total	100	100.0

Table 6. Association between nursing student's perception towards their profession with their demographic variables

Variable		Level of perception		df	Chi square value	Table value	Inference
		Good perception	Average perception				
Gender	Female	38	58	1	0.677	3.84	NS
	Male	2	2				
Religion	Hindu	36	48	2	0.304	5.99	NS
	Muslim	0	2				
	Christian	4	10				
Habilitation	Urban	24	42	1	0.301	3.84	NS
	Rural	16	18				
Birth order	First	24	32	4	0.433	9.49	NS
	Second	8	18				
	Third	2	6				
	Fourth	2	2				
	Above	4	2				
Nationality	Indian	36	58	1	0.169	3.84	NS
	Other than	4	2				

	Indian						
Family members/ Relatives in nursing	Yes	10	28	1	0.029	3.84	NS
	No	30	03				
Education of Father	Illiterate	4	2	3	0.038	7.82	NS
	Primary Education	6	8				
	Secondary Education	22	22				
	Degree	8	28				
Education of Mother	Illiterate	8	2	3	0.033	7.82	NS
	Primary Education	10	6				
	Secondary Education	14	28				
	Degree	8	24				
Occupation of father	Cultivation	10	10	3	0.015	7.82	NS
	Daily wage	14	08				
	Govt Employee	04	16				
	Private Employee	12	26				
Occupation of Mother	Cultivation	2	4	3	0.028	7.82	NS
	Daily wage	34	36				
	Govt Employee	4	12				
	Private Employee	0	08				

Table 7. Future intentions of B.Sc. Nursing students

S/N	Future Intention	Frequency	Percentage
1	Plan to go abroad	2	2.0
2	Higher education	42	42.0
3	Bed side nursing	26	26.0
4	Teaching Institutions	14	14.0
5	Nursing administrators	12	12.0
6	Change of profile	4	4.0

Present study found that out of 100 subjects, (40%) had ‘Good’ perception (60%) had ‘Average’ perception. Association between outgoing B.Sc. nursing students perception towards their profession with their demographic variables showing that Gender, Religion Habitation, Birth order of subject, Nationality, Family members/Relatives in nursing, Education of Father, Education of mother, Occupation of father, Occupation of mother were not significant. The hypothesis states that there is no relationship between outgoing B.Sc. nursing student’s perception towards their profession with their demographic variables. So the hypothesis H₁ were accepted. Notably highly with 42% of respondents were desire to do their further education after graduation.

The present study supported by Nursing Students Perception towards Profession and Future Intentions, Tirupati, Andhra Pradesh, illustrates the factors that motivated the participants to join in nursing. Majority (84%) stated that it provides an opportunity to settle early, 84% believed that nursing offers good opportunity to get a Government job. A relatively high percentage 71% stated that they are self-motivated to pursue nursing. 57% of students think that through nursing profession they can get blessing. Other reasons for choosing nursing include parents (29%) interest⁴.

Conclusion

From the findings of the present study, it was concluded that the perception about nursing profession among nursing students was good and average perception.

Conflicts of interest: The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

References

1. American Nurses Association: Nursing World, What is Nursing. Retrieved from <http://www.nursingworld.org>;2012
2. RCN (Royal College of Nursing). Defining Nursing. Retrieved from <http://www.rcn.org.uk>;2003.
3. Booth RZ. The nursing shortage: a worldwide problem. *Latin Am J Nurs.* 2002;10(3):392-400.
4. Swarna S. Nursing students perception towards profession and future intentions. *J Nurs Health Sci.* 2015;4(5):30-4.

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